

MOLECULAR PHYSIOLOGY AND GENETICS

PROSTHETICS WITH ALL-CERAMIC RESTORATIONS IN THE ORAL CAVITY

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Abstract

All-ceramic fixed prostheses represent a specialized area of prosthodontics. Veneers are often required to restore the anterior teeth. However, when the thickness of the ceramic veneer increases, there is a higher risk of chipping and an increased likelihood of pulpitis following tooth preparation. In such cases, it is recommended to perform endodontic treatment, restore the teeth with zirconia post-and-core restorations, and fabricate zirconia crowns with ceramic veneering.

Keywords: veneers; ceramic veneering; tooth preparation.

All-Ceramic Fixed Prostheses in Prosthodontics

All-ceramic fixed prostheses represent a specialized branch of prosthodontics; veneers are necessary for the restoration of anterior teeth. Key factors in planning the prosthetic restoration of a tooth include its topography and anatomical features (position, anatomical shape). It is important to consider the size of the hard tissue defect, the ratio of pulp to hard dental tissues (dentin, enamel), the type of occlusion, the direction of forces acting on the prosthetic restoration, the inclination of the tooth, and the results of radiographic examination.

Objective: To investigate the principles of tooth preparation and the features of forming a natural anatomical contour in all-ceramic restorations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To determine the color-optical characteristics of future prostheses, it is convenient to use the **Vitapan 3-D Master Shade Guide**, which characterizes the volume, saturation, and hue of the color. The first step is to determine the color of the canines (the most saturated color). The red scale is used to determine the dentin shade (initial scale), while the blue scale is used for the cervical and central areas of the incisors [1].

Indications for veneers:

- Tooth discoloration (fluorosis, defective fillings)
- Anatomical defects of teeth (chipping of the crown)
- Developmental anomalies of teeth (hypoplasia, imperfect amelogenesis)
- Abnormal tooth positioning (alternative to orthodontic treatment)

For achieving high-quality results with all-ceramic fixed prostheses, the following aesthetic criteria must be considered:

- Tooth shape
- Tooth position (axis inclination)
- Interdental space and level of contacts
- Gingival biotype
- Gingival color and gingival margin position
- Zenit of the gingival contour
- Tooth color (shades)
- Incisal edge level of anterior teeth
- Tooth surface relief
- Smile line and lower lip position [2]

Rules for veneer fabrication:

- Preparation should be limited to the enamel layer
- Veneers should be made only on vital teeth
- Whenever possible, preserve natural tooth boundaries (partial preservation of contact points if aesthetically feasible)

Contraindications for ceramic prostheses:

- Significant tooth malposition (lingual or palatal)
 - Major loss of hard tissues (>1/3 of crown)
 - Excessive tooth wear
 - Unrestored dental defects (incomplete prosthodontic treatment)
 - Deep bite
 - Parafunctional habits of masticatory muscles
- Before veneer fabrication, it is necessary to:
- Perform radiographic examination of the teeth to be restored
 - Assess oral hygiene and perform professional cleaning if needed

- Determine the final color of the restoration (with written patient consent)
- Replace all defective fillings
- Fabricate diagnostic models
- Optionally perform wax-up modeling on a cast or intraoral mock-up with fast-setting resin

- Take radiographs to evaluate pulp chamber location and enamel thickness

- Detect carious lesions
- Evaluate interdental spaces and contact points

Tooth preparation features for veneers:

- Cervical margin corresponds to the gingival margin
- Preparation margin is positioned 1 mm above the gingiva; in case of severe discoloration, the margin may be 0.5 mm below the gingiva

Preparation stages:

1. **Calibrating bur (round):** determine preparation depth depending on tooth size (cervical part 0.3 mm, equator 0.5 mm, incisal edge 0.8 mm) with water cooling
2. Create boundaries of the future veneer using the round bur
3. Prepare contact surfaces partially, preserving natural tooth contact points
4. Cervical area preparation: depth not more than 0.3 mm [1–4]
5. **Torpedo-shaped bur:** smooth incisions and thin vestibular surface; connect boundaries with fissure burs of corresponding diameter, starting with vertical aspects (proximal grooves – deeper on mesial, thinner on distal)
6. Final surface polishing using burs (red, yellow, white coding) and rubber polishing heads

This protocol ensures precise preparation and optimal aesthetics for all-ceramic veneers.

RESULTS

During tooth preparation, it is essential to preserve the **vestibular surface relief** of the tooth, repeating its natural anatomical shape. The **veneer thickness** should be uniform: different anatomical areas require removal of varying amounts of hard tissue (especially if the tooth is malpositioned), which can be guided using a **silicone key**. Contact with the opposing tooth's surface (incisal edge) should **not occur on the veneer surface or margin**, but only on natural tooth tissue [3–5].

Preference should be given to **palatal (lingual) preparation** with partial or complete coverage — contact with the veneer is preferable to contact at the enamel junction. Small mandibular incisors have limited retention, so the preparation margin should extend to the **upper third of the palatal (lingual) surface**; otherwise, there is a risk of chipping or marginal misfit.

The thickness at the incisal edge should not exceed **1 mm** [5, 6].

Veneers are usually cemented using **light-curing composite materials**. Excess material should preferably be removed with a **polishing bur**, not a probe, because probing may create **microgaps** between the cement, veneer margin, and tooth surface. Such gaps can lead to **plaque accumulation, decementation, and secondary caries** in the affected area.

Conclusions

In cases of significant diastemas (gaps between the central incisors) and when the patient refuses orthodontic treatment, creating **contact points on veneers** is a challenging clinical task, often resulting in a “spade-shaped” crown.

Additionally, if more than **one-third of the crown structure** is lost (moderate to severe wear, grades 2–3), using veneers becomes **risky** due to the increased thickness of the ceramic layer. This increases the likelihood of **veneer chipping** and the risk of **pulpitis** after tooth preparation.

Under such conditions, it is **preferable to perform endodontic treatment**, restore the tooth with **zirconia post-and-core structures**, and fabricate **zirconia crowns with ceramic veneering** for optimal durability and esthetics.

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